

RESEARCH ARTICLE

A Tour Guide's Performance Model for Sustainable Heritage at Borobudur

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Article Info:

Received 28 February 2024

Revised 21 June 2024

Accepted 23 June 2024

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This paper was presented at
International Conference on
Responsible Tourism and
Hospitality (ICRTH) 2023

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Abstract

Expanding the workforce in the tourism sector is a key aspect of the Rebuild Tourism for the Future via Sustainable Development initiative of which tour guides may become an essential part. Tour guide positions involve providing detailed explanations about heritage attractions and instructing tourists on acceptable behaviour during their investigation of these sites. This research is significant because tour guides play a crucial role in the preservation of tourism by safeguarding cultural treasures. Research on tour guides involves analyses that explore the subject from the viewpoints of their function, history, and structure. This study aims to enhance our understanding of the ecology of the tourism industry and heritage destinations by developing a model for the competent development of tour guides at Borobudur. Data was collected through participatory observation and in-depth interviews with six tour guides in Borobudur who are members of the Indonesian Tour Guides Association. The data were examined utilising Atlas Ti version 9. The study's findings suggest that implementing a high-quality curriculum and training programmes could lead to an exceptional performance model for tour guides at the Borobudur. The curriculum encompasses the implementation of four key components: (1) the scope of study, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching process, and (4) the assessment process. On the other hand, the training aspect covers four elements: (1) training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) evaluation.

Keywords: heritage destination, rethinking tourism, tour guide model

1. Introduction

The exponential growth of tourism is complemented by the implementation of Sustainable Development in Rebuilding Tourism for the Future, with a focus on advancing many sectors. Enhancing human resources is a crucial aspect in the development of sustainable tourism. This is highly significant, as humans are the focal point of sustainable development as the primary undertaking. These work opportunities can be found within the tourism industry, encompassing several sectors such as transportation, communication, attractions, rental services, entertainment, and the production of handicraft products or creative economy [1]. Hence, the establishment of tourism locations and products is intrinsically linked to the endeavour of cultivating proficient personnel, such as a skilled tour guide [1]. The tour guide is a participant in the tourism product chain who promotes and facilitates tourist activities. Tour guides play a crucial role in providing guests with precise information, enhancing their experience, and fostering a favourable perception of the location. Tour guides who possess extensive expertise have a significant impact on the overall quality of the tourist experience [2,3]. They serve as cultural mediators and intermediaries, facilitating communication and acting as responsible leaders, informants, educators, and consultants. Their main duty is to mediate cultural exchanges between tourists and inhabitants [4,5,6].

Studies on tour guides focus on analysing the role, origin, and structure of tour guides [7], identifying difficulties that arise during tourist guide activities [8], evaluating the quality of tour guide services [9], exploring tourist guide management [10], and proposing several tour guide models [11, 9, 12]. The study uncovers many facets of guided tours that are crucial for comprehending the intricacy of its operations and aiding the advancement of the profession.

By acquiring expertise in the field of tour guiding, individuals will be capable of performing their job with a high level of professionalism.

There is a significant demand for tour guides specialising in cultural heritage conservation. However, the investigation into the role of tour guides in safeguarding cultural assets is currently at its nascent phase. Tour guides play a crucial role in preserving cultural assets and promoting sustainable tourism by providing travellers with explanations on cultural heritage conservation. Ensuring the sustainability of the culture is of utmost importance. Tourists can gain an understanding of proper conduct in cultural heritage sites with the guidance of a tour guide. Furthermore, this project aims to address the existing gap in the ecosystem of Rebuilding Tourism for the Future Sustainable Development by implementing a model that enhances the skills and expertise of tour guides in the preservation of cultural heritage sites.

The argument acknowledges the need for incorporating environmental awareness into the tour guide curriculum, but it lacks particular illustrations of the content that should be covered in this training. To mitigate the adverse impacts of travel, the emphasis will be placed on educating visitors about environmental stewardship during their journeys. Adopting this mindset will decrease hostile behaviours and have a beneficial influence on society and the environment [13]. Sustainable tourism refers to the use of comprehensive systems and mindsets that promote the sustainable utilisation of resources [14]. The idea of sustainability was driven by the following key concepts: The four main areas of focus are: (1) preservation of the environment; (2) safeguarding human culture and variety; (3) promoting sustainable economic growth; and (4) implementing comprehensive development strategies [15]. Hence, the curriculum and training components necessitate a focus on environmental consciousness with the objective of enhancing sustainability. The process include instructing tour guides on ethical and environmentally sustainable tourism practices, with the aim of establishing a targeted strategy to mitigate the adverse environmental impacts of tourism. Visitors' positive experiences and satisfaction with tour guides' performances promote sustainable behaviour and reduce the negative effects on historical monuments [5].

Borobudur is one of the locations dedicated to the safeguarding of cultural heritage. Therefore, this study centres on developing a model to evaluate the effectiveness of tour guides in the Borobudur area. This strategy is founded on a curriculum and training programme designed to enhance the performance of tour guides.

2. Literature Review

2.1. Tour guide

Proficiency in the hospitality industry is crucial for individuals to effectively adjust their skills to the evolving needs and trends of the industry. One area of employment is the field of information technology. Proficiency in the skills and knowledge of tour guides is crucial for the future of tourism, as it ensures that tourists are content and inclined to revisit tourist locations. This is particularly important in the context of sustainable development. Tour guides are those that accompany visitors on trips, and in order to effectively perform their duties, they must possess and acquire specialised skills in a professional manner [1]. Tour guides are essential for several responsibilities within the tourism industry. These functions encompass tour guides as both communicators and ambassadors [9, 16]. They possess the ability to establish positive rapport with tourists [17], necessitating a professional approach to their work.

Another role of tour guides is to ensure that tourists are compelled to return due to the exceptional experiences they have, particularly while seeing heritage sites [18]. These guides provide detailed instructions and descriptions of historical locations during guided tours of these significant sites [19]. Efficient guiding approaches can mitigate the adverse effects of tourists on cultural places by promoting environmentally conscious behaviours among visitors [20]. Tour guides can enhance their competence by undergoing tourist education [21,22] and engaging in rigorous training programmes [23] to obtain expertise, information,

and skills [6] necessary for achieving competency. Proficient tour guides can ensure tourist satisfaction and encourage return visits [2].

2.2. Heritage tour guide

Heritage places hold importance as tourism destinations that focus on promoting cultural awareness [24]. One of the tourism complexes is included as a World Heritage Site. Due to their increasing popularity, cultural heritage tours have grown more captivating to visit. Consequently, there is an increasing influx of tourists with a wide range of ideas and personalities. The presence of many characteristics and behaviours, such as littering, vandalism, and pollution, might have a detrimental effect on the area [25]. Nevertheless, a tour guide can identify this, along with other factors, by monitoring the path traversed [19]. The primary role of this tour guide is to advocate for the preservation of the environment and cultural heritage, so encouraging tourists to embrace sustainable and ethical practices [26]. It is crucial to provide guidance to tourists regarding appropriate behaviour and effective exploration tactics. By implementing a sustainable tourist experience, the utilisation of interpretation by a knowledgeable guide proves to be an effective technique in reducing the detrimental impact of tourists on heritage objects [27,28]. Nevertheless, the aptitude associated with the performance of this important position still has to be determined. Despite the crucial role that tour guides play in excursions, some of them have not yet reached the pinnacle of their knowledge. Tour guides' performances have a significant direct influence on tourists' satisfaction with their services and a secondary influence on their whole tour experience [11]. It is essential to identify the suitable model of tour guide competence..

2.3. Tour guide competency model

Competence is a term that is associated with a job environment where someone is skilled and capable [29]. There are five key elements that define competence: (1) motivation, (2) character, (3) concept, (4) science, and (5) skill. This competent persona are An individual who demonstrates competence in their profession typically excels in their performance [30]. Competence is a motivational concept that drives individuals to achieve proficiency [31], and to acquire the necessary skills and expertise in their professional sector [32]. Competencies will alter an individual's approach to job duties, emphasising both technical and behavioural performance. This competency ensures that the performance appraisal process effectively identifies and evaluates the specific aspects that are being examined and provides clear guidelines on how to conduct the assessment. The application of performance appraisal pertains to the evaluation of competence and determining the methods and criteria for assessment. These qualities pertain to situations where performance is required, as well as skills in communication and providing service [33]. In this instance, the evaluation of performance is linked to these specific talents, thereby necessitating the use of various competency models in their enhancement.

The tour guide competency model that has been examined is a training strategy that promotes sustainability and transformation [17]. This model places a greater emphasis on providing direction for ecotourism, namely in terms of training, personal attributes, and attitudes towards environmental stewardship. Moreover, the tour guide competency model is adapting to fulfil the requirements of the tourism industry. This model prioritises aesthetics during operation [11]. Evaluation of task orientation, constructive behaviour, and counterproductive attitude among tour guides. The competency models for tour guides in underdeveloped countries primarily emphasise training tour guides to enhance their sustainable ability [35].

2.3.1. Curriculum

The curriculum is intricately linked to the organisation and delivery of competencies for tour guides. The programme encompasses the current competencies. The education curriculum encompasses knowledge, skills, and innovation [36], which serve as a framework for enhancing learning in the field of tourism [37]. The selection of skills, information, and attitudes incorporated into Indonesia's tourism curriculum is based on their effectiveness [38]. The application comprises four components: (1) the study's scope, (2) content standards, (3) the teaching procedure, and (4) the assessment process. This study primarily

examines the correlation between the curriculum and the extent of study pertaining to tour guides, which is considered the most crucial aspect. The tourism curriculum incorporates skills related to tourist performance, including the integration of tour guide competences within the core curriculum [39]. The inclusion of the tour guide skills curriculum as a core curriculum can serve as a valuable resource for enhancing competency development.

2.3.2. Training

Good training is an inseparable part of curriculum. To be able to achieve competence, multiple processes must be constructed and put on practice, such as training, professional certification and tour guide licences. Training is a process of knowledge transfer [40]. This tour guide competency training can be carried out properly by implementing the references regulated in the curriculum. Training [29] is a systematically planned program which contains four stages (1) identification of training needs, (2) types of training, (3) trainers, and (4) follow-up and evaluation. These four stages need to be implemented in order to possess the ability for improving tour guides' performance. Tour guides' performance can be improved by training in tour guiding [41]. Tour guides need to get training for themselves to perform effectively and reach competent capacity. Tour guide training will support their competence [42].

3. Methodology

This study employed qualitative methodologies. The data was gathered through in-depth talks and interactive observation. Subsequently, a comprehensive dialogue occurred, involving six tour guides from the Borobudur region who are affiliated with the Indonesian Tour Guides Association. Informants are qualified guides who have a competence certificate, have been working for at least 5 years, and have fluency in a foreign language. The questions related to the curriculum, training, and performance based on hospitality and outstanding service. And they actively contributed to the data collection process by conducting thorough interviews and engaging in participatory observation. The data were examined via Atlas Ti version 9. Atlas/Ti is a software programme designed for the analysis of conveyed messages [43]. This part comprises a qualitative analysis that elucidates the responses to research inquiries subsequent to conducting interviews with informants. The stakeholders' comprehensive explanations, actions, and observations from the interview were classified in this research. The analytical resources produced by Atlas. TITM make a valuable contribution to scientific research, particularly in the field of social sciences [43,44].

The analysis phase consists of multiple processes, commencing with the input of curriculum and training data through coding. Next, the data is processed and examined to discover the theories and concepts acquired by the researcher. The subsequent sections will provide a comprehensive analysis of each theme in order to construct the conceptual framework of the Tour Guide Performance Model in Borobudur.

4. Results and Discussion

Borobudur is a renowned cultural site in Indonesia. The temples of Borobudur, including Borobudur and Mendut temples, have been officially classified as heritage sites. Heritage sites necessitate exploration under the guidance of a tour guide. The investigation conducted at Borobudur disclosed that tour guides had a track record of expertise. The stages of understanding the curriculum for the tour guide and completing the training were crucial in developing this ability. Both of these components establish a structure for the model that this study will embrace. This concept can be utilised to revitalise tourism in the future by focusing on sustainable development, particularly in heritage destinations.

Tour guides has the necessary expertise to instruct and elucidate to tourists the appropriate conduct to be observed at the heritage site, acquired via comprehensive curriculum study and training completion. Tour guides have acquired expertise in this process of leading tours. The implemented curriculum effectively enables tour guides to understand the notion of guiding heritage through coaching provided by teachers who has competence in the

business. In order to obtain professional tour guide certification, tour guides must successfully complete various sorts of tests as part of their education and training requirements. Upon achieving proficiency, individuals will receive a certificate of competence, which can be utilised to obtain their identity card.

The identification of training needs, the various types of training, the selection of trainers, and the evaluation process are all components of training. Similarly, the curriculum encompasses the area of study, content standards, the teaching technique, and the assessment process. Thus, tour guides can effectively fulfil their role by recommending that tourists wear appropriate attire, such as clothing and sandals (Upanat), when visiting Borobudur Temple with an environmentally responsible mindset. In addition, it imposes limitations on the amount of tourists allowed to visit the Borobudur Temple and prohibits them from ascending the monument, littering, or defacing its walls with graffiti. The investment viewpoint of this tour guide is expected to impact the long-term viability of tourism by preserving and promoting cultural assets.

Figure 1. Borobudur Heritage Site

4.1. Curriculum

4.1.1. Scope of study

The adopted curriculum incorporates studies that are interwoven with the cultural diversity curriculum, enabling tour guides to comprehensively grasp the content and effectively use it in their profession. The curriculum has been consistently implemented and strategically designed to incorporate innovative elements that can be utilised by tour guides. The tour guide curriculum development model is a framework that showcases the application of curriculum through the demonstration of attitudes, ideas, characters, and processes. It aims to facilitate the mastery of associated information.

Tour guides in the Borobudur area have adopted the Innovate service Organisation and Management Model to enhance their service to tourists, alongside the curriculum. This is evident in the manner in which they provide information while providing guidance employing

thematic approaches in the Borobudur area. This theme approach offers travellers the opportunity to experience the tour guide process with flexibility.

4.1.2. Content standards

The content standard contains references to learning that will be derived from subject matter by providing opportunities and structured freedom for tour guides to improve the mastery of technical competencies (hard skills) and work culture (soft skills) applied at the Borobudur (Heritage destination location). It was found that the curriculum was prepared by competent parties from the association of Indonesian tour guide associations. In addition, in the curriculum there is also an allocation of achievement time in accordance with the tour guide scheme which contains benefits.

4.1.3. The teaching process

The training approach encompasses the acquisition of expertise in Borobudur, the cultivation of a service-oriented mindset towards tourists, and the utilisation of foreign languages for effective storytelling. The teaching process involves the proficient delivery of presentation content that is comprehensible through the use of modules. This training module is disseminated based on the content presented with an effective teaching methodology and in alignment with the number of tour guides available.

4.1.4. Assessment process

The training approach encompasses the acquisition of expertise in Borobudur, the cultivation of a service-oriented mindset towards tourists, and the utilisation of foreign languages for effective storytelling. The teaching process involves the proficient delivery of presentation content that is comprehensible through the use of modules. This training module is disseminated based on the content presented with an effective teaching methodology and in alignment with the number of tour guides available.

4.2. Training

4.2.1. Tour guide performance training needs

Tour guide training in Borobudur as Heritage destinations focuses on the following skills:

- 1) Knowledge Base: Historical, Cultural Knowledge and Local Insights especially Borobudur as Heritage Destination. Tour Guide have understood well about the history, culture, and philosophy in Borobudur and also able to explain information about history, local culture, local customs and recent developments in the area.
- 2) Quality Service: as good tour guides, they have to have a good hospitality services and problem-solving skills. They have to know how to handle unexpected situations and solve problems at Borobudur Heritage Destination and also have a customer-centric service mindset, focusing on making the tour enjoyable and memorable for participants.
- 3) Communication Skills: tour guides have to have a good public speaking, language skills, and interpersonal skills. Tour guide should present performances using effective public speaking techniques, including voice projection, articulation, and engaging storytelling to international tourists.
- 4) Good Navigation: tour guide has to create and know the route planning and includes an interesting route, time schedule and total number of tourists handled. It is included in emergency procedures for evacuation procedures and first aid basics for tourists.
- 5) Environmental Awareness: tour guides need to explain Sustainability by teaching tourists the principles of sustainable and responsible travel by explaining the use of special sandals and special clothing when at Borobudur Heritage Destination.
- 6) Cultural Sensitivity: training that provides understanding for guides to be sensitive to cultural differences and tourist behaviour.

4.2.2. Tour guides types of training

The training offered to tour guides at Borobudur, specifically at heritage destinations, encompasses classroom instruction, practical exercises, and on-the-job learning through

exploration of the Borobudur region and its environs. This method involves employing techniques in the form of introductions, leading material, and closing.

4.2.3. Tour guide compliance trainers

The training for tour guides in the Borobudur region is conducted by experienced tour guides from the Indonesian Tourist Association, as well as international tour guide professionals and local guides familiar with the heritage region. This is highly beneficial for the revitalisation of tourism in the future, particularly for heritage areas, by promoting sustainable development.

4.2.4. Tour guide evaluation

This evaluation is a practical assessment of tour guiding skills in the Borobudur historic region. It is conducted by the Tour Guide Professional Certification Institute and the Indonesian Tour Guide Association of Central Java to determine the level of competence in guiding tours.

The outcomes of Borobudur's Tour Guide Performance Model are determined by two factors: the curriculum and the training provided:

- 1) The resolution and determination of conflicts can be achieved when tourists encounter challenges, as these tour guides offer appropriate solutions.
- 2) Problem-solving skills refer to the capacity of tour guides to recognise issues, examine potential solutions, and effectively apply the most optimal course of action.
- 3) Interpersonal skills refer to the capacity to regulate one's own behaviour, possess a strong sense of empathy, and exhibit effective leadership qualities.
- 4) Possessing innovation skills and the ability to improve technology is essential for adapting to technological advancements.
- 5) Critical thinking and decision making necessitate the ability to engage in intellectual reflection, independence, and rationality. This encompasses the capacity to offer interpretation that is both instructive and contentious, based on observations, information, and reasoning.
- 6) Collaboration refers to the capacity to cooperate and engage with tourists and fellow colleagues.
- 7) Self-confidence refers to the state of having a strong belief in one's ability to effectively perform the responsibilities of a tour guide.
- 8) The proposed concepts and solutions aim to create a joyful and welcoming atmosphere for guidance.
- 9) The Borobudur tour guides have effectively produced the guide material to ensure that tourists understand and remember their intended purpose.

Historical site research is the examination of artefacts and architectural structures to understand the evolution, origin, and context of societies. The ultimate aim is to draw historical conclusions. Tourists would have a clearer comprehension of the cultural significance of the presented history and the knowledge gained from the tour if they were accompanied by a tour guide. The tour guide enables travellers to comprehend and learn about the cultural legacy present in Borobudur. The present study was based on the performance of tour guides, which served as a demonstration of their competency as tour guides. This strategy also recognises the crucial role that the talents of qualified tour guides play in historical sites. The literature evaluation suggests that the effectiveness of tour guides at Borobudur in terms of their proficiency is influenced by the curriculum and training they get.

The literature study suggests that both curriculum and training are essential components. The establishment of favourable interactions between tour guides and tourists can be influenced by the adoption of curriculum and training programmes. Positive encounters of this nature are anticipated to enhance tourist happiness and augment their understanding of heritage places, thereby leading to an improvement in promotion through word-of-mouth. The study will then examine the long-term viability of the location by evaluating the actions of visitors and the effectiveness of tour guides at the historical site.

Figure 2. The tour guide’s performance model

This research has discovered multiple issues. Initially, it was observed that the tourists' enhanced consistent conduct was notably impacted by the tour guide's proficiency. Sustainability training is a crucial subject integrated into the curriculum. Tour guides who have received proper training are capable of accompanying tourists on cultural trips [9]. Several distinct research investigations offer empirical evidence for the importance of tour guides' performance in ensuring tourist satisfaction [35,45,46]. Based on this study, travellers who are content with their tour guides are significantly more likely to express inquiries regarding sustainability concerns. This satisfaction is the result of the tour guide's proficient advisory services at historical heritage sites, where they aid tourists in maintaining the cleanliness of the environment, appreciating the attractiveness of the site, and promoting conservation. This greatly affects the sustainable behaviour of both tourists and caretakers at conservation sites.

Furthermore, the findings confirm that the experiences of visitors significantly influenced the relationship between sustainable behaviour and the performance of tour guides [13,14]. Tour guides assist travellers in their efforts to preserve cultural heritage places. These actions have the potential to mitigate environmental impact, promote the preservation of cultural heritage, and garner support from tourists in relation to environmentally sustainable activities. The fact that tourists visiting Borobudur heed the recommendations of tour guides to recognise the importance of preserving cultural heritage serves as proof of this phenomenon.

Although this research primarily examines the curriculum and training of tour guides, there is always room for improvement, particularly in terms of connecting the field of tourism sciences with other academic subjects.

5. Conclusions

The Tour Guide Performance Model at Borobudur is a development concept aimed at revitalising tourism in cultural destinations by focusing on sustainable development. This model prioritises the curriculum and training of heritage tour guides. And the recommendation on this, they should be collaborate with professionals such as cultural experts, historians, and archaeologists. Furthermore, on hospitality service requires proficiency with technology, including social media and digital marketing. This will build long-lasting relationships with tourist. By implementing these recommendations, tour guides in

Borobudur are expected to improve the quality of their services, create an unforgettable tour experience, and support the sustainability of these cultural heritage destinations.

Author Contributions

IPHH: Writing - Original Draft, Writing-Review & Editing, Visualisation and Investigation; **JD**: Review & Editing, Supervision; **S**: Review & Supervision, and **JS**: Review & Supervision.

Conflicts of interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

Acknowledgements

I Putu Hardani Hesti Duari, have been awarded a PhD scholarship. The funding for this study was provided by the Puslabdik Education and Culture Ministry and LPDP. The Ministry of Finance of the Republic of Indonesia.

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